

Applying Racist Nativism Theory to K–12 Education Policy in Arizona, 2000–2010

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There are approximately 40 million Latina/o foreign-born immigrants living in the United States, according to the US Census Bureau's American Community Survey. Moreover, approximately 22 percent of all elementary and secondary school students in the country (youth ages 5–18) speak a language other than English at home (US Census Bureau 2011a, 2011b). In Arizona, this translates to approximately 150,000 English language learners (ELLs), or 13 percent of all K–12 enrollments. The overwhelming majority of these ELLs are Spanish speakers, with the percentage of Mexican-origin Latina/os at 90 percent (Arizona Department of Education 2010). Policy makers in Arizona, as in many states, are looking for models to address the educational needs of the growing ELL population.

Given Arizona's large immigrant population and the pervasive anti-immigrant climate in the state, a critical analysis of Arizona education policy can shed light on the educational experiences of Latina/o immigrants more broadly at a time when antipathy to them is rising in many parts of the country. A great deal of media attention has been paid to the detrimental effects of Arizona's anti-immigrant laws such as SB 1070 and HB 2281. There has been less focus on education policy that reflects similar anti-immigrant sentiment, that is, language and curricular policies that promote assimilationist approaches within K–12 education.

This article uses Lindsay Pérez Huber and colleagues' (2008) concept of racist nativism, informed by Latina/o critical race theory (LatCrit), as an analytic tool to examine education policy in Arizona. After articulating a theoretical framework, we examine Arizona as a case study, looking at

assimilationist practices in education affecting immigrants and citizens of Latina/o heritage. We focus on contemporary education policy from 2000 to 2010, particularly language and curricular mandates (Proposition 203, the four-hour English Language Development block model, and HB 2281), to unveil the continuing marginalization of Latina/os in Arizona's K-12 educational system. We conclude by describing the overarching effects of these policies and their implications for state leaders and policy makers in Arizona and other states.

Racist Nativism through the Lens of Critical Race Theory and LatCrit

In order to understand racist nativism, it is important first to understand its relationship with critical race theory. Critical race theory grew out of a black-white binary understanding of race that failed to capture some important issues and nuances applicable to the experiences of racialized groups. Critical race theory allows researchers to examine and challenge the multiple forms of oppression that systematically affect people of color (Ladson-Billings 2009; Pérez Huber 2010). It is a framework or set of basic insights, perspectives, methods, and pedagogies that seek to identify, analyze, and transform the structural and cultural aspects of society that maintain the marginal position and subordination of people of color (Crenshaw et al. 1995).

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Critical race theory starts with the premise that race and racism are endemic and permanent. Racism is understood to occur at micro and macro levels, to take individual and institutional forms, to include both conscious and unconscious elements, and to affect individuals as well as groups (Davis 1989). Although race and racism are seen as central, they also intersect with other forms of subordination, including gender and class discrimination. Thus, critical race theory has a social and racial justice research agenda that works to empower people of color, paying particular attention to the experiential knowledge of individuals. It uses an interdisciplinary perspective to challenge dominant ideologies, including meritocracy, colorblindness, race neutrality, and equal opportunity, that camouflage the self-interest, power, and privilege of the dominant group (Ladson-Billings 2009).

Building on critical race theory, critical Latina/o theory expands the exploration of civil rights analysis beyond race. Conceived as an anti-subordination and anti-essentialist theory, LatCrit is concerned with a progressive, coalitional Latina/o pan-ethnicity. It seeks to articulate the experiences of the Latina/o community by examining their unique forms of oppression (Pérez Huber 2010, 2011). LatCrit is used to reveal the ways Latina/os experience race, class, gender, and sexuality while also acknowledging issues of nationality, language, immigration status, ethnicity, and culture (Delgado Bernal 2002). More specifically, it challenges the dominant paradigms of immigration discourse that have distorted or erased the experiences of undocumented Latina/os. For this reason, LatCrit is more a political than a racial movement. It attempts to link theory with practice, scholarship with teaching, and the academy with the community (LatCrit 2001).

Nativism is an ideology based on the perceived superiority of the native-born, an assumption used to justify native dominance over the “nonnative.” Nativist movements in the United States have historically targeted specific groups according to racialized perceptions of who fits and does not fit into the “American” national identity. Nativist ideology undergirds efforts to exclude immigrants from full participation in US society by limiting their political, social, and legal status (Galindo and Vigil 2006). It has also, since at least the nineteenth century, figured in the process of defending national identity from perceived foreign threats (Higham 1955).

Following tenets of critical race theory and LatCrit, racist nativism places racism at the core of its conceptualization of the native. A racist-nativist conceptual frame helps researchers understand how the historical racialization of immigrants of color has shaped the contemporary

experiences of Latina/o immigrants (Pérez Huber et al. 2008). Notions of white supremacy and privilege are used to support racial hierarchies, which operate on the basis of a system of racial domination and exploitation in which power and resources are unequally distributed (Bonilla-Silva 2001). Hegemony of the English language, similarly, is utilized to maintain social domination over linguistic minority (nonwhite) groups (Macedo, Dendrinos, and Gounari 2003). These notions of superiority position whites as the entitled beneficiaries of unearned societal privilege and status and normalize white values, beliefs, and experiences as uniquely legitimate (Gillborn 2006).

The fashioning of a dominant national identity is based on a normalized belief that whites are inherently native and natives inherently white. Thus, Pérez Huber et al. (2008) merge the notion of racism with that of nativism and define racist nativism as “the assigning of values to real or imagined differences, in order to justify the superiority of the native, who is to be perceived white, over that of the non-native, who is perceived to be people and immigrants of color, and thereby defend the right of whites, or the natives, to dominance” (43). We utilize this definition in our analysis of Arizona to highlight the effects of the state’s approach to Latina/o education policy.

Racist Nativism in the Arizona Context

The racist-nativist movement in the US Southwest has deep historical roots. America’s racialized past abounds with examples of oppressed people being denied their languages, histories, and cultures through enforced indoctrination. Naturalization laws have been designed to limit immigration and restrain the economic and political rights of those considered inferior. After appropriating Mexican land in 1848 at the end of the US-Mexican War, white Americans took control of the political and social system of the newly gained territory, which included the present-day states of California, New Mexico, and Nevada along with parts of Colorado, Arizona, Utah, and Oklahoma. This formalized the culture of racial domination and exploitation (Acuña 2000).

In an effort to provide the still-developing United States with labor and capital, the US Congress permitted open borders throughout most of the nineteenth century and the first decades of the twentieth. This allowed the migration of large numbers of Mexicans, who sought to escape the violence of the Mexican Revolution or to find work in the emerging agribusiness industry

north of the border. By the 1920s, the US government moved to close off the flow. Immigration restrictions passed in 1921 and 1924 established the Border Patrol and provided for deporting immigrants who entered without visas; this was followed by legislation in 1929 that criminalized unlawful entry. Temporary labor shortages during World War I and World War II, however, led the United States to reopen the gates. While US industries needed cheap labor, Mexican families were drawn by the promise of work, freedom, and opportunity—a classic example of interest convergence (Bell 1980).

However, in Arizona and throughout the Southwest, racist-nativist approaches were already being used to segregate Mexican-origin children and provide them an inferior education. In this era before *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954), Mexican-origin children were shunted into “Mexican” schools and classrooms (the so-called “Mexican room”) in order to separate them from their Anglo, English-speaking peers (Gándara and Orfield 2010). This segregation systematically produced much lower academic achievement and much higher dropout rates for Mexican-origin students (USCCR 1972). The effect was to create an unequal distribution of power and resources.

Today, Arizona continues to pass and enforce assimilationist laws and policies that undermine the civil rights of immigrants and US citizens of Latina/o heritage. Supporters of such measures allege that Latina/o immigrants are not integrating well into the American mainstream and threaten the prosperity and cultural identity of the state and nation. The aggressive enforcement of portions of SB 1070, Arizona’s landmark anti-immigrant law, has resulted in the hurried exodus of over 100,000 Latina/os from the state (BBVA Research 2010). The law has “uprooted and separated families, atomized communities and [brought about] the disintegration of existing social and economic support networks” (Corazón de Tucson 2012, 27). Many Latina/o immigrants are opting not to report crimes to the police, visit physicians or hospitals even in emergencies, or send their children to school in order to avoid official scrutiny and the possibility of detention and family separation (Lopez 2011). SB 1070 has affected all Arizona Latina/os, including US citizens, legal immigrants, and undocumented immigrants, especially those in mixed-status families, who fear that one or more members could be deported.¹

Perhaps most severely affected are Arizona’s Latina/o children, a vulnerable population who now must “deal with pervasive fear and uncertainty, smaller and less-resourced schools, and a growing mistrust of institutions meant to serve them” (Lopez 2011, 2). Against the backdrop of the

anti-immigrant hostility sweeping the state, we now turn to contemporary Arizona education policy and its effects on Latina/o immigrants' ethnic identity and the quality of education they receive.

Contemporary Arizona Education Policy, 2000–2010

Over the past decade, K–12 education policies in Arizona have taken a restrictive approach toward language and curricula and have systematically diminished the quality of education that Latina/os receive (Mahoney et al. 2010). Of particular significance are Proposition 203, English Language Education for Children in Public Schools; Arizona Revised Statutes §15-756.01, imposing the four-hour English Language Development block model; and HB 2281, which effectively shut down Tucson's Mexican American studies program.

ENGLISH-ONLY EDUCATION IN THE PUBLIC SCHOOLS

Prior to 2000, Arizona school districts could select from a variety of program models, including various forms of bilingual education, to promote English proficiency and academic achievement for their ELL students. In November 2000, however, Proposition 203 was passed. The new law ended the flexibility that local districts had enjoyed regarding the choice of program models for ELLs and required all districts to implement a one-size-fits-all Structured English Immersion model (Gándara and Hopkins 2010). According to the statute, Arizona public school children are to be “taught English by being taught in English . . . during a temporary transition period not normally intended to exceed a year” (Arizona Revised Statutes §15-752). All of the books and instructional materials used in class must be in English, and teachers can use only minimal communication in the students' native language. After a year of the structured immersion, they are to be mainstreamed into regular classes.

Although the empirical studies are limited, there is currently no evidence to support the claim that ELL students are doing better as a result of Proposition 203's requirement for English-only education (Wright and Choi 2006). Several studies have concluded that it takes more than one year, generally four to five years or more, for students to achieve a level of proficiency in English sufficient to pass most English-language proficiency tests (Collier and Thomas 1989). In fact, research has shown the Arizona English-only program to be ineffective, with fewer than 11 percent of

the state's ELL students achieving proficiency in a year's time (Mahoney, Thompson, and MacSwan 2004).

A recent study compared the achievement outcomes of ELL students in New Mexico and Texas (states that offer bilingual education) with those in Arizona, Massachusetts, and California (English-only states) on the National Assessment of Educational Progress. It found larger gaps in achievement between English learners and native English speakers in states with English-only instructional policies (Rumberger and Tran 2010). Similarly, studies by the National Literacy Panel (August and Shanahan 2006) and the Center for Research on Education, Diversity, and Excellence (Genessee et al. 2006) found that reading instruction in a student's home language facilitates reading achievement in English, and spelling and writing in the first language relates in important ways to literacy development in English. This suggests that English learners who receive some native-language instruction are at an advantage compared with their peers in English-only settings (Thomas and Collier 2002).

Bilingual education programs, blamed for the high dropout rates and low English literacy of many immigrant children, have been curtailed or eliminated in many school districts across the country. ELLs have been subdued by eliminating their native languages from the classroom and assimilating them to the dominant culture via a deficit approach toward learning English. Meanwhile, students who are native English speakers are encouraged to partake of dual-language programs aimed at developing bilingualism and multicultural competence through an additive approach (Lindholm-Leary 2001). In other words, while Anglo students are allowed to maintain their native language and add another language for enrichment, immigrant children are forced to abandon their native language under the English-only model. This double standard ultimately exploits the richness of ELLs' language and culture for the benefit of the dominant culture while further subjugating linguistic minority groups.

Consistent with the definition of racist nativism, this English-only policy promotes the perceived superiority of the native over the nonnative. It normalizes white values, beliefs, and experiences as legitimate while devaluing the language and cultures of Latina/o Spanish-speaking immigrants. In this way it supports the hegemony and dominance of English. Because one cannot effectively separate language, culture, and learning, the English-only mandate ultimately does not allow non-English-proficient Latina/os equal access to educational opportunities, as it claims. Rather, the elimination of bilingual education programs has negatively affected

the academic achievement and educational experiences of ELLs (Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010).

THE FOUR-HOUR ELD BLOCK

State regulations regarding English-only instruction became even more restrictive after Arizona implemented in 2007 what is now called the four-hour English Language Development (ELD) block (Mahoney et al. 2010). This model requires English learners to receive ELD services in an English-only immersion setting for a minimum of four hours per day for the first year in which they are classified as ELL, and in subsequent years until they achieve English proficiency (Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010). The model requires ELLs to be grouped based on their English language proficiency and to be taught phonology, morphology, syntax, lexicon, and semantics as separate subjects. In other words, the four-hour ELD block perpetuates segregation by classroom as students are separated from their peers along racial, ethnic, and linguistic lines. This affects the quality of curriculum and instruction they are exposed to (Gándara and Orfield 2010).

According to some education scholars, the four-hour ELD block completely disregards research in the field of second language acquisition and cognitive infrastructure associated with second language development (August, Goldenberg, and Rueda 2010; Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010). There is currently no body of scientifically based research that recommends the isolation of ELLs for four hours a day in English language classes, where they are kept from participating in core academic content and cognitively rich instruction (Krashen, Rolstad, and MacSwan 2007). The four-hour ELD block is especially problematic for older students who must pass standardized writing and content-based exams in order to graduate from high school (Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010).

Russell Rumberger and Loan Tran (2010) found that the variable that explains the greatest amount of variance between the achievement outcomes of ELL and non-ELL students is the degree of segregation they experience. The isolation of ELLs from mainstream students and classrooms for four hours a day negatively affects the social and cultural well-being of these students by silencing them within the greater school context, diminishing their sense of belonging to the educational environment, and limiting their chances for academic success (Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010; Osterman 2000). The four-hour ELD block model thus

exacerbates the existing segregation of Latina/o students, isolating them not just by school but by classroom. It puts these students at high risk for school failure and dropping out by returning them to the pre-*Brown v. Board of Education* “Mexican room” (Gándara and Orfield 2010, 4).

By excluding limited English speakers from core academic content and cognitively rich instruction, the ELD block model prevents ELLs from receiving the same educational experiences as their English-proficient counterparts. In this sense it perpetuates racist-nativist ideology. It positions native speakers as the entitled beneficiaries of unearned privilege and status within the Arizona educational context while relegating ELLs to second-class citizenship and a subpar quality of education. “In order to progress in language learning, ELLs need ample opportunities to interact with those beyond their own level of proficiency, and to hear and participate in language and cognitive activities that involve academic content” (Garcia, Lawton, and Diniz de Figueiredo 2010, 3). Segregation by language proficiency reinforces the perceived superiority of the native and the subjugation of the “nonnative” and, ultimately, the unequal distribution of access and resources.

TUCSON’S BAN ON ETHNIC STUDIES

Arizona HB 2281 was signed into law on May 11, 2010, just weeks after SB 1070. Aimed squarely at the Tucson’s Mexican American studies (MAS) program, HB 2281 effectively prohibited Arizona school districts and charter schools from offering programs of instruction, courses, or classes that (a) promote the overthrow of the United States government, (b) promote resentment toward a race or class of people, (c) are designed primarily for pupils of a particular ethnic group, or (d) advocate ethnic solidarity instead of the treatment of pupils as individuals (Arizona Revised Statutes §15-112).

The goal of Tucson’s MAS program, part of its ethnic studies program, was to boost achievement among Hispanic students by providing them with curriculum materials embedded in Hispanic history and culture (Gómez and Benton 1998). But the MAS curriculum was held to be in violation of HB 2281 in January 2012. As a result, the Tucson Unified School District was required to eliminate its MAS curriculum or face sanctions that would include losing 10 percent of its state funding—approximately \$15 million for the 60,000-student district (Horne 2010). This politically fueled ultimatum resulted in over 100 books being banned from classrooms.

The state's move to shut down the program disregarded the significant improvement in achievement among students with exposure to the Mexican American studies curriculum. Results from an impact analysis of the Tucson MAS program suggest that there is a consistent, significant, positive relationship between MAS participation and student academic performance (Cabrera, Milem, and Marx 2012). Similarly, an audit conducted by Cambium Learning for the Arizona Department of Education found multiple measures indicating that the MAS curriculum increased student achievement and was helping to close the achievement gap. The auditors found that "in each of the last six years, students who failed the reading and writing AIMS subtests in their sophomore year and then took a MAS course during their junior year were indeed more likely than the comparison group to pass these two AIMS subjects by the end of their junior year" (Casteel, Gilzean, and Faulkner 2011, 45).² Students who enrolled in MAS courses had higher graduation rates than those who did not, by a margin ranging from 5 percent in 2005 to 11 percent in 2010, and students who took a MAS course in their senior year were more likely to graduate than students who did not (Casteel, Gilzean, and Faulkner 2011).

The audit found no evidence to suggest that any classroom within the Tucson school district was in direct violation of the law. Nonetheless, the district's school board was forced to end the MAS program in order to prevent a \$4.9 million reduction in their February 2012 allocation from the state budget.

Far from targeting only immigrants, Tucson's ban on ethnic studies prevents the implementation of a culturally relevant pedagogy that can collectively empower many students to experience academic success and develop a critical consciousness (Howard 2001). Such a pedagogy makes learning more relevant to students who have traditionally been marginalized from the mainstream curriculum by validating their culture and their contributions to the classroom. In a district that is more than 60 percent Latino, teaching Chicano history and literature is crucial for students' sense of belonging and academic development. Tucson's ban on ethnic studies promulgates racist nativism by de-ethnifying the curriculum and excising the histories of Mexican Americans, Native Americans, and other non-Anglo ethnic groups. It effectively precludes minority culture from becoming an accepted part of the Arizona educational mainstream. According to Paulo Freire (2000), the most effective way to weaken ethnic identity is by controlling and distorting young people's knowledge about their culture, history, values, and language. Conversely, programs and curricula that

provide this knowledge allow subordinate groups to become conscious of their reality and their oppression. Therefore, education can either reinforce racial domination or promote empowerment and emancipation.

Unlike SB 1070, the intention of HB 2281 is not to make the experiences of Latina/o immigrants so unpleasant that they self-deport, but rather to inculcate a deep-seated second-class status by denying Latina/os of Mexican descent the right to explore their own histories and cultures. The ethnic studies ban forcibly imposes the values, beliefs, and culture of the majority group by teaching US history only from the majority perspective and excluding differing historical accounts. Consistent with racist-nativist theory, this approach ultimately normalizes the perspective of the dominant group—whites—and perpetuates their privilege. The result is the eradication of ethnic identity among young people and the systematic enforcement of racial hierarchies through censorship of knowledge.

Conclusions

Employing a racist-nativist lens embedded in a LatCrit framework, this article has demonstrated how Arizona education policy from 2000 to 2010 rejected approaches to education that build on students' cultures and native languages. English-only policies and English immersion models, the four-hour ELD block, and the elimination of the MAS program deny Latina/os access to political, social, cultural, and language rights and promote cultural homogeneity and assimilation. They emulate pre-*Brown v. Board of Education* educational models by promoting segregation and a lower quality of education for minority students. Beyond the adverse effects of these policies on the educational achievement of Latina/o students, the reinforcement of English hegemony and subjugation of linguistic minority groups further disenfranchises ethnic communities and perpetuates racial hierarchies. Similarly, the segregation and marginalization of English language learners, especially through the four-hour ELD block, maintains the unequal distribution of power and resources in K–12 education and forces a return to the “Mexican room” for ELLs (Gándara and Orfield 2010, 4). Lastly, the removal of culturally relevant pedagogy and teaching from the Arizona curriculum, as evidenced by Tucson's ban on ethnic studies, hinders students' ability to develop a broader sociopolitical consciousness and engage critically in social issues.

Institutional practices and structures that preclude students from culturally engaging in the classroom undermine students' cultural capital

and inhibit the development of genuine relationships that support students' achievement (Valenzuela 1999). Assimilationist approaches toward ELL education, therefore, have negative consequences for immigrant populations, particularly when students are led to abandon their native language and ethnic ties. For these reasons, state educational policies that reflect racist-nativist approaches, consciously or not, are reducing the access of Latina/o immigrants to educational opportunity and decreasing their chances of social and economic mobility.

According to Sandy Baum and Kathleen Payea (2005), a society's economic success is linked to its citizens' education, as higher levels of education correlate with lower levels of unemployment and poverty. Low investments in education, consequently, produce economic adversity for all, not just the undereducated, as adults with lower levels of education tend to rely more on social safety net programs that strain public budgets. Suppressing their native languages, de-ethnifying the curriculum, and relegating ELL and Latina/o youth to remedial classrooms is, therefore, not just exacerbating systematic racism and assimilationist practices but is also limiting our opportunities for economic growth and prosperity as a society.

In an age of globalization and international competition, when many other countries have more than just one official language, the goal should be to develop the talent within even our most underprivileged communities, not to stifle and discourage their equal participation. The most important policy lever that states could use to increase the achievement of ELL students is to reduce the segregation they experience in their schooling (Rumberger and Tran 2010). Incorporating bilingual education and ethnic studies programs into K–12 education not only will help increase motivation but may boost academic achievement and help narrow the achievement gap. When Latina/o students have exposure to their language, culture, and history in the classroom, the quality of the education afforded them improves, and this can shift the way ELL students, in general, are received in the classroom.

In order to combat the movement to eliminate bilingual education and ethnic studies programs across the country, further research should be done on the sociocultural and educational benefits of these programs. Evidence that these programs and services are benefiting not just pupils of a particular ethnic group but the society as a whole may help deter racist-nativist approaches to education policy. Instead of viewing cultural and linguistic differences as barriers and “subtracting” students' cultures and languages from the curriculum, education policy should seek to create

“additive” learning environments (Vásquez 2003). Arizona language and curricular education policy needs to take into consideration the local context of school districts, available resources, variations in the needs of the students served, and existing research before prescribing value-driven educational approaches that impose the experiences, values, and beliefs of the white majority.

State policy makers in Arizona and across the country should seek to develop the human capital of their Latina/o populations through education by integrating students’ native languages and cultures into the curriculum. Unless the educational needs of our most vulnerable populations are addressed, they will continue to be relegated to second-class citizenship and society will be deprived of their contributions.

Notes

1. A family in which one or both parents are noncitizens and one or more children are US citizens.
2. Arizona’s Instrument to Measure Standards (AIMS) is a standards-based assessment that measures student proficiency in meeting the state’s academic content standards in writing, reading, mathematics, and science. It is required by state and federal law.

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